

ANALYSIS ON THE APPLICATION OF SONGS IN INTERNATIONAL CHINESE TEACHING —TAKING UZBEKISTAN INTELLEKT SCHOOL AS AN EXAMPLE

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Abstract. *This article takes the songs used in the children’s Chinese classroom of the sixth grade of Intellect School as the research object and analyzes the use situation of chants in teaching. Firstly, we summarize and sort out the songs used, then analyze the characteristics of the above songs based on the content of the songs and combine with teaching cases, then combine the questionnaire survey of students to summarize the advantages and problems of the songs used, and finally put forward targeted suggestions and measures.*

Keywords: *children’s Chinese classroom, Songs, Suggestions and measures*

1. Introduction

The songs discussed in this article are still produced in international Chinese classrooms, closely related to students' learning content, and composed by teachers (Zhou Xiaokang, 2010). Taking the Intellect School where the author teaches in Uzbekistan as an example, studying songs which is applied in the primary school sixth-grade Chinese classroom.

2. Analysis of the characteristics of songs used in Chinese classroom

From January to September 2023, the author used a total of 9 songs in the classroom, including children's songs, rhythm songs, musical nursery rhymes, ancient poems songs, etc. The students who learned all the songs were 6th grade students from school.

In terms of the source of the songs, 5 of them were adapted by the author, and the remaining 4 were selected on the YouTube platform. The reference resources for compiling the songs are mainly online digital resources. In terms of content and purpose, the songs used are mainly based on pinyin and classroom management, and are used respectively for the teaching of 6 finals and all initial consonants as well as discipline management to guide students to concentrate and prepare for lesson, the transition before the end of the course and the adjustment of students' emotional state. In terms of music composition of songs, there are 5 songs with compositions, all of which are from online resource platform.

3. The role of the songs used in children’s Chinese classroom

3.1 Songs have diverse contents and uses

In addition to pronunciation and classroom management content, the song’s content also includes word teaching, activities and games, all of which are closely integrated with the classroom. The same song can also be used flexibly and diversely in various contents and play different roles.

3.2 Facilitate students to understand and learn Chinese teaching content

Most of the songs used are short, concise and rhythmic, and the students are happy to take the initiative to repeat them. Through repeated readings consciously and subconsciously, learners can be stimulated and strengthened to associate words, pinyin, Chinese characters and carry out associative memory. In the questionnaire survey, when asked about the role of learning Chinese

songs, 83% of students chose "it helps me understand and learn new words and sentences", indicating that many students also recognized that songs have brought them this benefit.

3.3 High operability in classroom practice

First of all, children's Chinese learning is based on interest, so it is necessary to create a relaxed and lively teaching environment. Most of the songs used by the author are close to life and full of childlike interest. Some actions are also added to help students understand. These actions have also become one of the elements that activate the classroom atmosphere, making the songs more acceptable to students.

Secondly, all the songs used have achieved specific goals to varying degrees in actual teaching, making it easier for teachers to use them in the classroom.

4. Problems arising from the songs used in children's Chinese classroom

4.1 Songs lack learning content in Chinese characters, cultural knowledge

Each lesson of the textbook used by the author also includes the content of learning Chinese characters, but there is a lack of corresponding songs to assist students in learning. In the questionnaire survey, 26% of students hope to learn Chinese characters in class. If songs designed for the content of Chinese characters can be used, more students may be attracted to learn Chinese characters.

In addition, 43% of students hope to learn "Chinese cultural knowledge ". This option ranked second among the multiple-choice questions. The songs used by the author did not introduce Chinese cultural into them. This is the content that needs to be supplemented by the songs.

4.2 Some songs lack supporting compositions and animation videos

Most of the songs adapted by the author do not have the function of singing and cannot fully mobilize the learners' auditory senses. In addition, many of the songs adapted by the author do not have supporting animation videos. In the questionnaire survey, 78% of students thought that "classroom with animated videos" would be an interesting class. It is found that in teaching, animated videos will quickly attract children's attention and concentration. Therefore, for their own the songs adapted still need to be improved in the production of animated videos.

4.3 Failure to consider the difficulty levels of songs

In teaching practice, some songs can make it difficult for Uzbek children with no basic knowledge or basic Chinese proficiency to learn. In addition, the same song has different levels of difficulty for children of different grades. One of the main reasons for this phenomenon is that the author did not predict and judge the actual Chinese level of overseas children to write, design and evaluate the difficulty of the songs. At the same time, author did not make detailed difficulty assessment rating of the songs according to the specific age stages of the children.

5. Suggestion and measures for the usage of songs in the classroom

5.1 Adapt the song content with reference to resources or use it directly

It is relatively easy for teachers to learn from existing song resources, combine the teaching materials they use and the content they want to expand, and adapt or re-write the lyrics of the songs. Teachers can also collect song resources closely related to the teaching content and apply directly to the classroom. Finally, they can also pay attention to the melodies and music of other songs other than the teaching content and fill in the lyrics themselves according to the melody. This also solves the problem of songs that cannot be sung because without music.

5.2 Make full use of technical software and websites

Among the songs adapted by the author, the "Initial consonants rhythm song" comes with accompanying composition and animation video, all of which were realized using technical software and websites. In the questionnaire survey, when students were asked which of the songs they had learned was their favorite, 22% of the students chose this song, which ranked second among students' favorite songs, which is relevant with animated videos . Therefore, in the subsequent adaption of songs, it is also necessary to make full use of various technical software and websites to produce animated videos and audios for the songs.

5.3 Grade the difficulty of the songs and adjust the level of the songs

In Chinese teaching, teachers also need to provide appropriate song materials to students at different ability levels, so it is also necessary to grade the difficulty of songs. Therefore, teachers can grade songs according to different grades, taking into account the length and difficulty of the sentences and the number of chinese character. On the other hand, the teaching process is dynamic, and the content of the songs will be updated along with the teaching. Teachers can update the content of the songs and adjust the rating of the songs at any time.

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